

Pilot Evaluation 5: Una Europa citizen science Toolkit

Final Version

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Summary

The Citizen Science Toolkit is a pilot project dedicated to citizen science. This project has a dual focus on two transformation modules: embedding citizens and society and strengthening human capital. Its primary goal is to remove obstacles hindering cross-border and cross-sectoral R&I collaboration by empowering Una Europa early-stage researchers to initiate citizen science projects.

The project adopted a structured four-step approach. The initial phases involved mapping strategies, policies, support services, and best practices in the field of citizen science. Data was collected through two questionnaires distributed to administrative staff, researchers, and university policy makers across the Alliance. Additionally, a series of webinars showcasing exemplary citizen science projects and a cartography of citizen science initiatives in two Focus Areas, One Health and Cultural Heritage, was developed. The subsequent phases focused on brainstorming sessions and workshops organised by the Citizen Engagement Cluster. These sessions aimed to facilitate an exchange of experiences, delve into challenges, and propose potential solutions to enhance citizen science within the Alliance. After collating and providing a synthesis of the outputs from the brainstorming sessions and workshop, the pilot concept was developed and presented during an additional brainstorming session in September 2022 in Edinburgh.

The pilot consists of eight interviews, representing the eight universities participating in the Una.Resin project, conducted with researchers who are experts in the field of citizen science. Each interview addresses key aspects of citizen science, such as project design, citizen engagement, impact evaluation, and advice for early-stage researchers. These interviews are publicly accessible on the Una Europa website and are accompanied by guidelines distilled from the insights shared within them. Together, these interviews and guidelines form a toolkit that researchers engaging in participative research can use in the preparation of a citizen science project. Importantly, the toolkit is licensed as an Open Education Resource, aligning with Una Europa's commitment to openness, inclusivity, and the dissemination of innovative work.

The pilot's main **outcome** is the production of a Citizen Science toolkit, comprised of educational support materials for implementing citizen science projects. This toolkit increases awareness of various citizen science practices and methodologies, benefiting researchers at all career stages. In addition, the toolkit offers recommendations aimed at institutions and alliances on how to enhance citizen science initiatives and amplify citizen participation in research. It also helps research managers understand how to better support citizen science projects. Finally, the toolkit provides participating researchers with a platform to showcase their projects to a broader audience and lays the foundation for a network of researchers who specialise in participatory research.

The project holds the capacity to mobilise a cultural transformation among researchers,

research support officers, and policymakers, which would further lead to a shift in the R&I landscape of Una Europa universities. The project seeks to catalyse an increase in the number of citizen science projects and stimulate collaborative, interdisciplinary projects that address global issues.

Considering the interdisciplinary nature of projects, **lessons learnt** from the pilot project highlight the importance of embracing a wide definition of citizen science. Collaboration with stakeholders, experts in citizen science, and other researchers (for Una Europa, the self-steering committees of the Focus Areas) will be crucial in further developments of the pilot, and for ensuring the project remains both relevant to its intended beneficiaries and responsive to their needs. Therefore, a clearly defined and coherent understanding of the target group from the project's outset is essential.

The pilot project suggests a clear and reusable format that can be scaled up. It could be extended to other disciplines or Focus Areas, providing a multifaceted perspective on participative practices. At the same time, the format could be upgraded via more active involvement of citizens and third parties (i.e., not the researchers). The toolkit could be expanded to encompass networking events or by including additional support materials in a variety of formats. If the toolkit proves to be successful overtime, there may be potential to transform it into an online educational course.

Objectives and aims of the pilot

The Citizen Science Toolkit is a pilot project dedicated to citizen science and aimed to address the “Embedding Citizens and society” transformation module. As part of WP3, it also plays a role in bolstering the “Strengthening Human Capital” transformation module. The pilot targets early-stage researchers and aims at enhancing their transdisciplinary skills that are crucial to diversifying their career paths. By promoting more open, inclusive, and transparent research the pilot also contributes to the “Comprehensive mainstreaming of Open Science practices” transformation module.

The pilot addresses several barriers to cross border and cross-sectoral R&I collaboration:

- Lack of sustainable and accessible knowledge-sharing formats: A significant challenge lies in the absence of sustainable and easily shareable formats for exchanging knowledge.
- Limited awareness of partner universities' expertise and projects: There is often a lack of awareness about the expertise and ongoing projects within partner universities. This issue is particularly prominent in the context of citizen science where the visibility of initiatives is usually insufficient.
- Deficiency in interdisciplinary proficiency: An essential element in promoting cross-sectoral collaboration is having the necessary interdisciplinary expertise. Citizen science projects, in particular, frequently require collaboration across diverse domains, necessitating a wide range of expertise.
- Lack of networking opportunities: The lack of networking opportunities hinders the ability to bring together specialists from different disciplines who are addressing common global challenges.

This pilot aims to animate institutional change by developing material for the integration of

science and society in curricula (e.g., covering STEM, public engagement, ethics, gender), and enlarge the scope of R&I activities by fostering informal science education (museums, science centres), promoting citizen science, and engaging civil society actors and citizens. The desire is to foster Open Science and open access to scientific results and data (e.g., online open notebooks, OERs, open data, etc.) in relation to citizen science projects. The main target group of the pilot project are early-career researchers, with the secondary target group being researchers at any stage of the career who are interested in participative projects and/or willing to initiate a citizen science project. The main beneficiaries are researchers, including early-stage researchers, with research support managers and policy makers being secondary beneficiaries.

In the early stages of the project design, it was essential to take into account other Una.Resin pilot projects. To avoid creating multiple online platforms that were similar, it was decided to steer the pilot project toward alternative formats. Despite discussions regarding the potential benefits of a Citizen Science Hub, the decision was made to create an online platform designed to facilitate collaboration between researchers and citizens. This platform sought to be a solution to address the numerous bottlenecks in the enhancement of citizen science practices.

The experience of the Cultural Heritage self-steering committee played a significant role in shaping the pilot project's concept. The self-steering committee had already been working on joint projects that were participative in nature. One of these projects, the Cultural Heritage at The Edge (CUTE) project (2021-22) developed within the 1Europe project (funded under the Una Europa seed funding initiative), served as an example from which to develop the toolkit. The continuation of this project, CUMET-Cultural Heritage in The Metropolitan Peripheries, 2023-2026, JPI CH (Joint Programming Initiative on Cultural Heritage), also includes collaboration with citizens.

The experience of the self-steering committee illustrated the need to develop knowledge of citizen science methodologies and the skills for effective engagement of citizens across Una Europa universities. Consequently, it appeared crucial to harness expertise in citizen science practices to assist potential research teams in planning and executing collaborative projects that incorporate citizen participation. Moreover, with the existence of the UnaHerDoc joint doctoral program in Cultural Heritage, the pilot project's results will directly serve PhD students enrolled in this program.

The idea and format for this pilot were also influenced by the OER Toolkit developed during the 1Europe project. This served as both a model and inspiration for creating support materials that are open and accessible to all.

Initial design and implementation of the pilot project

One of the primary goals of the Una.Resin project is to reshape the institutional structure of member institutions, enabling them to proactively address the upcoming global challenges. This transformation encompasses frameworks that actively engage citizens and non-academic entities across all regions within the Una Europa ecosystem and throughout every phase of the R&I process, and thus, provided the rationale for inclusion of dedicated citizen science pilot. Citizen science serves as an effective tool to close the gap between science and society, promoting openness and enhancing the overall impact of research. By involving

citizens in research initiatives, universities are working towards the democratisation of knowledge and strengthening trust in scientific research.

The initial phase of the Una.Resin project further supported the need for a dedicated citizen science pilot. The mapping and brainstorming exercises conducted in the initial phase underscored the universities' strong dedication to citizen engagement, yet also highlighted a deficiency in the support for, understanding of, and infrastructure around citizen science. Consequently, the decision was made to concentrate the pilot project's efforts on enhancing awareness of citizen science, sharing exemplary approaches, and consolidating expertise.

As an integral component of WP3, this pilot project is also aligned with the overarching goals of this WP, which revolve around enhancing the capabilities of early-stage researchers by equipping them with transversal skills that can facilitate diverse career paths. In this context, the primary target audience for this pilot project comprises early-stage researchers. Its central objective is to inform early-stage researchers about the various manifestations of citizen science, elucidate its benefits, requirements, and impact, and strengthen their abilities in project design and implementation. The pilot project, therefore, investigates the possibility of co-producing knowledge on citizen science through the exchange of best practices. Additionally, it explores the feasibility of converting the know-how required to initiate a citizen science project into a transversal skill or a set of transversal skills needed to achieve impactful and responsible research.

To accomplish these objectives, it was decided that the project should take shape in the form of a toolkit. The Una Europa Citizen Science Toolkit comprises eight interviews conducted with renowned researchers, representing eight Una.Resin universities, who are experts in the field of citizen science. These experts were asked eight questions addressing the following key aspects: 1) project presentation, 2) project design and funding, 3) citizen engagement, 4) the role of citizens, 5) identifying bottlenecks and barriers, 6) evaluating impact and sustainability, 7) examining institutional support and recognition, and 8) advice for early-stage researchers. The interviews have been made publicly accessible on the Una Europa website, accompanied by guidelines distilled from the insights shared within them. Consequently, the toolkit offers first-hand knowledge grounded in personal experiences and forged through this collaborative activity. Importantly, the toolkit is licensed as an OER, aligning with Una Europa's commitment to openness, inclusivity, and the dissemination of innovative work for the benefit of a wider community.

A four-steps approach was applied to the pilot. The first two steps were primarily focused on mapping the strategies, policies, support services, and best practices in the field of citizen science. The data collection was carried out through different questionnaires shared with administrative staff, researchers, and university policy makers. The acquired data was analysed based on the following two documents: Mapping HR Strategies and Priorities for Joint Strategy (Una.Resin Deliverable 3.1.) and Analysis of the Open Research Support Services and Practices (Annex Una.Resin Deliverable 2.2). Additionally, a series of webinars were organised to showcase exemplary citizen science projects and a cartography of citizen science initiatives in the One Health and Cultural Heritage Focus Areas.

The subsequent two phases revolved around brainstorming sessions and workshops organised by the Citizen Engagement cluster. These sessions aimed to facilitate the exchange

of experiences, delve into challenges, and propose potential solutions to enhance citizen science within the Alliance. An essential milestone in this endeavour was the co-creation workshop, which was held online on 1st July 2022. During this workshop, participants discussed various aspects of citizen science, including the types, methodologies, challenges, and potential formats for institutional collaboration aimed at sharing support structures. One of the most important outcomes of the workshop was the mapping of potential solutions to bolster citizen science, categorised into four areas: 1) project incubator, 2) sharing of best practices, 3) training, and 4) support services. These steps, alongside the associated collected inputs, provided a foundation from which to develop the first idea for the pilot action, which was presented and discussed during the brainstorming session held in Edinburgh on 29th September 2022.

After developing the pilot concept, a session was organised with the researchers involved in the project to obtain their insights. Notably, the feedback from the researchers was used in formulating the interview questions, ensuring their relevance to all research projects. The interviews conducted with the researchers can also be seen as a source of data collected via the project. This data was subsequently analysed and utilised in the formulation of the recommendations that accompany the videos within the Citizen Science Toolkit. Feedback was also sought from PhD students enrolled in the joint PhD program in Cultural Heritage via a brief online questionnaire.

The pilot was designed and implemented by the Citizen Engagement cluster. Cluster members of each university were responsible for identifying experts for the interviews and for connecting with local audio-visual services during the production phase. As the decision was made to concentrate the pilot on cultural heritage, consultations were held with the Cultural Heritage self-steering committee. The self-steering committee expressed their interest in the pilot and approved the suggested format. Furthermore, in one of the interviews, the CUTE project, initiated by the self-steering committee, was featured as an example of a citizen science project.

A number of challenges arose during the design phase. Firstly, the list of actions needed to enhance citizen science at the level of the Alliance was extensive, and it was challenging to decide which needs should be addressed in the first place. Hence, the final concept of the pilot project addresses several needs: raising awareness, showcasing best practices, pooling expertise, and developing joint support materials. Secondly, the project faced challenges related to its scope, timeline, and available resource. Many initial concepts required significant financial investment, as well as the acquisition of additional expertise. Thus, the final concept of the pilot project was built in a way that ensured all the work could be done by the Citizen Engagement Cluster and without extra funding, outsourcing only the production of the videos. Finally, it was hard to estimate the sustainability within the timeline of the Una.Resin project, as the impact of the toolkit could not be fully understood by the end of the project. However, once the pilot is published, it does not require any maintenance and it can be continuously used without any assistance.

There were also challenges in the implementation phase. It was a challenge to find relevant experts in Cultural Heritage as, in some universities, citizen science projects are still mostly associated with environmental or hard sciences. Furthermore, researchers do not always identify their projects as citizen science even though they engage citizens and are profoundly

participative. To this end, the range of the disciplines and engaging practices was kept as broad as possible, with participant researchers coming from different disciplines (historians, cultural heritage managers, archaeologists, linguists, etc.) and often employing different practices to engage citizen. Despite difference in discipline and methodology, all researchers had an interest in cultural heritage. Not all universities had available audio-visual services for the production of the filmed interviews. These universities could connect their researchers with UP1, who provided the required audio-visual service.

Outcomes and impact of the pilot project

The primary achievement of the project is the development of educational support materials on how to initiate and run a citizen science project. These materials, in a form of a toolkit, are accessible to the public through the Una Europa website, and their open licensing ensures that they can be widely used. This openness is particularly advantageous for educators who can leverage these materials in their upcoming projects.

By harnessing the expertise from eight Una Europa institutions, the project enabled a collaborative production of new knowledge, which took the form of a set of recommendations complementing the videos within the toolkit. Furthermore, the project has generated recommendations aimed at institutions and alliances, offering guidance on how to bolster citizen science initiatives and amplify citizen participation in research. The pilot project has also provided participating researchers with a platform to exhibit their projects to a broader audience. It has allowed them to present their work from a fresh transdisciplinary perspective, placing a strong emphasis on the involvement of citizens. Moreover, the project effectively increases awareness of various citizen science practices, methodologies, and strategies for engaging citizens. As a result of this initiative, researchers at all career stages can gain a deeper comprehension of participatory approaches and may find inspiration to initiate their own citizen science projects. The project also provides a means for researcher to enhance their capabilities to successfully launch such projects. For research managers, the project provides a better understanding of how to support citizen science projects, identifying the specific assistance they may require. The pilot brought together eight Una Europa experts in citizen science, laying the foundation for a network of researchers specialising in participatory projects. It has pioneered a new format that can be applied to the creation of support materials across various disciplines or for other interdisciplinary topics.

The project aims to produce a transformative shift in the R&I landscape of the Una Europa universities. By raising awareness and providing guidelines and recommendations on how to initiate citizen science projects to our primary audience, the pilot aims, in the long term, to catalyse a surge in the number of citizen science projects or projects that involve participatory elements. It also has the potential to stimulate the creation of collaborative, interdisciplinary projects that tackle current global issues, effectively bridging the gap between science and the pressing needs of society. Overtime, the initiative may have a cascading effect, leading to a more significant cultural shift towards deeper citizen engagement in R&I. Moreover, the ability to initiate citizen science projects can be viewed as a cross-cutting skill applicable across all disciplines. Cultivating cross-cutting skills empowers researchers to open new pathways in their careers.

The cultural transformation expected as a consequence of the project is not necessarily confined to researchers; it has the potential to extend to research support officers and

policymakers. For instance, this transformation could influence the evolution of research support offices, prompting the creation of more customised assistance for citizen science projects or the establishment of essential infrastructure to facilitate collaboration with external stakeholders.

The primary objectives of the Una.Resin project centre around barrier-free collaboration in R&I. This encompasses forging new pathways for collective research endeavours, sharing experiences, and co-creating new knowledge. Through this pilot project, experts in Citizen Engagement could map institutional practices related to citizen science and facilitate the exchange of experiences. The toolkit itself represents an innovative approach to jointly constructing knowledge; researchers not only share their insights through interviews, but their collective experiences result in a set of recommendations for implementing citizen science projects. The project, therefore, exemplifies how pooling expertise can yield new and innovative knowledge.

One of the most significant outcomes of the project is the enhanced understanding that researchers gain regarding citizen science practices. This heightened awareness has the potential to boost the number of citizen science and participatory projects, thus stimulating initiatives aimed at addressing societal challenges. In essence, the pilot project directly contributes to the goal of making R&I within the Una Europa Alliance more impactful and responsive to global challenges.

The recommendations derived from the project not only pertain to the conception and implementation of citizen science projects but also encompass how universities should guide and support citizen science. These recommendations directly tackle the issue of building a collaborative research ecosystem involving non-academic stakeholders, including citizens.

The structure of this pilot was intentionally designed to have broad reach and accessibility. The Citizen Science Toolkit has been made publicly available on the Una Europa website ensuring access for a wide audience, and the CCBY license is attributed to the content making it free to use in other projects. To enhance accessibility, English subtitles have been included in the videos. The format of short 3-5-minute responses was selected to make the content engaging. This attractiveness is crucial for the pilot's objective of increasing awareness.

The pilot's format can be readily expanded and adapted by other universities or alliances. This format can be outlined in five distinct steps:

1. Determine the project's scope, identifying the specific academic disciplines, Focus Areas, or thematic focus that will be emphasised.
2. Identify the suitable participants who possess the experience and expertise relevant to the project.
3. Collaboratively formulate interview questions that are universally applicable to all the projects within the pilot, generating a set of five to eight core questions.
4. Conduct interviews with concise responses, ensuring that answers to each question do not exceed three to five minutes in length.
5. Compile the recommendations by distilling the insights from these experiences and synthesis the findings for each question, thereby generating new knowledge from the collective expertise.

It is important to highlight that the Citizen Engagement Cluster provided an input to the Una.Resin R&I Strategy. The Cluster made a proposal regarding the sustained collaborative efforts to improve citizen engagement practices, including citizen science, throughout the Una Europa Alliance. This proposal has been highly influenced by the learnings gained from this pilot project. Secondly, the project itself conveys a lucid message to the institutions regarding the support they can offer to researchers for the advancement of citizen science. A set of recommendations directed at institutions and alliances has been distilled from the interviews and forms an integral component of the project. These recommendations encompass the following suggestions:

- Offer educational resources that guide researchers in applying for grants involving citizen engagement activities.
- Deliver training programs focused on refining relevant project management skills.
- Aggregate expertise in citizen science methodologies, creating a centralised knowledge hub for researchers.
- Establish a repository of available funding sources.
- Provide researchers with toolboxes on possible stakeholders and associations of citizens organised to support with engaging citizens.
- Propose tailored assistance in reaching out to local communities.
- Allocate funding opportunities for experiments, allowing researchers to explore innovative research methods on a smaller scale.
- Foster a network of citizen science experts, providing an opportunity for a recurrent knowledge exchange and collaboration.

Sustainability of the pilot project

As the work on barrier-free collaboration in R&I transitions from Una.Resin into the Una.Futura project, it is possible that the outcomes of this pilot will have an influence on forthcoming Una.Futura activities. This influence is particularly relevant in the context of Una.Futura WP4, which has been tailored to extend and build upon the Una.Resin activities, with a specific emphasis on training early-stage researchers. If the knowledge of how to initiate a citizen science project is recognised as an essential, cross-cutting skill, the pilot project can be continued in the form of training. Moreover, the pilot project may find a natural continuation in the activities of the self-steering committees scheduled during the Una.Futura project period. Many self-steering committees have already underscored citizen engagement and collaboration with non-academic actors as vital tools for fortifying their infrastructures and networks. The future scaling-up of the project beyond the conclusion of Una.Resin currently lacks a definitive roadmap. A critical prerequisite for the project's continuity hinges on the ongoing efforts of the Citizen Engagement cluster, which should persist into the Una.Futura lifecycle.

Generally, the pilot project format does not inherently demand extra funding, relying primarily on the universities' in-kind contributions. Nonetheless, if a university lacks a specialised service for audio-visual content production, this particular aspect of the project may necessitate external funding and outsourcing. Furthermore, it is important to ensure the availability of support staff to oversee the project's progress and handle the synthesis of interview content.

Lessons learnt

The key lessons learnt from the pilot project can be summarised as follows:

- Embrace a wide definition of citizen science: Some researchers engage in participatory research practices without explicitly labelling their projects as citizen science, so inclusivity is vital to find participants.
- Consider interdisciplinary: Even if a project is primarily focused on a specific discipline, it is crucial to acknowledge that many citizen science projects are inherently interdisciplinary. These projects can span various fields, making rigid classification problematic.
- Collaborate with self-steering committees: Collaborating with self-steering committees is vital to ensure ongoing interest and engagement from research teams. Their involvement can guarantee beneficiaries of the project.
- Co-create questions with participating researchers: Engage in the collaborative process of formulating questions with researchers who will take part in the interviews. This ensures that the questions align with the specifics of their research projects, making the interviews more relevant and meaningful.
- Define clear target groups: It is crucial to determine the primary audience and the key beneficiaries and it should be understood that these groups may vary in their awareness regarding citizen science practices and in their experience and skill level.

Recommendations for the future

Several suggestions on how to scale up the pilot project can be formulated:

- Organise a networking event: While the project does not require researchers to be acquainted, organising an online or offline networking event can be valuable. Fostering connections among researchers interested in citizen science can lead to the creation of a network that consolidates the project's results.
- Incorporate citizen and partner perspectives: Although it presents logistical challenges, involving citizens and associated partners in the interviews can be of benefit. Their insights can provide a unique and valuable perspective, enriching the overall content and offering a more comprehensive view of citizen science initiatives.
- Broaden the project scope to other disciplines: Maintain the project's current structure while extending its reach across various disciplines, Focus Areas, or themes. This approach introduces a discipline-specific perspective, highlighting particular challenges and tactics. By encompassing multiple cases from diverse fields, the project will offer a diverse array of practices and methodologies.
- Provide other support materials: Transform the Citizen Science Toolkit into a foundational resource that serves as a basis for creating complementary materials. These additional resources can take different formats and employ various approaches to engage researchers. The ultimate goal is to establish an online, freely accessible knowledge hub.
- Develop an educational course: Explore the possibility of enhancing the project's format to create an educational course. This may involve bolstering the educational aspects and using the toolkit as a cornerstone for crafting an online course, providing structured learning opportunities. The course can be seen as a progressively expanding pool of information that evolves over years.